
AN OUTLINE OF RELEVANT LITERATURE ON INNOVATIVE SCHOOL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

Leadership could be a holistic approach to education. When executed with zeal and vision, it ends up in a greater knowledge of the attitudes of scholars. The renewal and implementation of creative leadership practises could be a significant tool for varsity improvement. The effectiveness of college is vast area of research in Education. The research during this area has primarily intensive on leadership and innovative practices in schools. The leader should catalyse fun and thrill while leading students rather than burden and tedium. School leadership is currently a top priority for education policymakers all round the world. Increased school autonomy, likewise as a stronger specialise in education and performance, have necessitated a rethinking of the role of college leaders. Professionalizing school leadership, supporting current school leaders, and making school leadership an appealing career for future candidates all have space for improvement. The function of leadership is one in all the foremost critical aspects in effective program execution. The supply of current creative instruments has resulted in well-organized procedures in class administration. To remain up with globalisation, educational administrators have integrated creative approaches resulting from the introduction of latest school administration systems. So as to supply exceptional work, leadership plays a vital part within the creative and innovative process.

Keywords: Innovation, leadership, leadership practices, professionalize, critical, globalization, creative.

1. INTRODUCTION

In education, leadership has long been thought to be extremely important. Educational leadership may be a multifaceted field of study. It's the foremost researched topic in behavioral science. It's thought to be a way via which an individual leads others. in line with the definition of Bass (1990a: 19) "leadership consists of influencing the attitudes and behaviors of people and also the interaction within and between groups for the aim of achieving goals." Net et al. (2004) defines leadership because the processes where by one individual influences others too willingly and eagerly direct their efforts and skills towards attaining define organizational goals. Leadership plays a pivotal role in enhancing organizational creativity (Mumford et. al 2002; Amabile et.al, 2004), launching and driving innovation projects (stoker et.al 2001). Leadership is ultimately related to certain goals. These goals may be broad visions of promising future states, but they will even be very solid targets. In either case, leadership points towards a direction which always directed towards the goal of innovation.

Innovative leadership entails introducing something novel, like a brand new concept, approach, technique, process, product, or discovery, so as to deal with current issues and meet people's needs now and within the future. in step with Kouzes and Posner (2013), leadership behavior are often well thought-out by practice including: displaying the way (i.e. setting personal examples), motivating a shared vision (i.e. talking about future goals), thought-provoking the method (i.e. willing to do innovative techniques) permitting others to act (i.e. allowing people to create choice) and promising the center (i.e. praising people for employment well done). In step with Sena (2012) shown that innovation leadership could be a new development to resolve future problems, in generating new ideas in a very certain form practiced for the help of people organizations and its applications will result in change. a replacement wave of research on educational leadership has long-established that the standard of leadership practices in an exceedingly school can make significant differences to the educational and successes of scholars (Davidson, 2014).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The review of literature has provided a short overview of important concepts associated with the leadership, innovation, innovative practices, its techniques and areas and leadership in-schools

Leadership

The infrastructure, culture, and teachers of a college are all influenced by leadership. Learning outcomes are significantly influenced by direct effects on the organization, culture, and teaching and learning environment. Leadership in education over and another time stands within the spotlight, mostly due to growing accountabilities for varsity principals and also the accountability-driven environment they add (Hitt & Tucker, 2016; Leithwood, 2010; Muijs, 2010). Fullan (2007), leadership is 'the process of persuading by which a private (or leadership team) prompts a gaggle to chase objectives

held by the leader or shared by the leader and his or her followers'. Fiedler (1967) may be a forerunner in defining leadership in terms of true. His leadership model, the 'Leadership Contingency Model', endeavours to indicate how leadership depends on the case. He has gone beyond the outmoded concept that's authoritarian leadership. He classifies a gaggle situation to leader in terms of three variables a) Leader's social relationship together with his group b) leader's power and witness c) structure of task allotted to the group leader. This classification gives an actual idea or concentration on leader's individuality. Williams (2015) scrutinized that the ability of educational leadership within the era of globalisation with the changing aspects of multifaceted quality competition requires leaders who innovate, having the ability to yield a spread of guidelines and operationalization of structural work, a lust and dedication to figure clearly to achieve the tutorial goals he leads. Leadership's moral honesty is critical to quality improvement management; the leader in an exceedingly quality improvement organisation clearly represents the range of leaders and managers. In general, quality improvement is worried with values, setting the course, and allowing individuals to realize macro and micro goals. In step with Yukl (2002), the term leadership itself ventures images of powerful, forceful individuals who command successful armies, build prosperous and significant empires, or vary the course of states. Zekan et al. (2012) publicized that leadership is someone who has the talent and encourage, monitor his dependents effectively, and implement programs that are established together in progressing education into a excellence school education and synergize to innovate.

Leadership in schools

Schools are socially built organisations, and educational administration and leadership are people-intensive endeavours. Getting things done in a school takes a lot of face-to-face connection with teachers and other students. For making successful school enhancement efforts, Glickman et.al (2001: 49) build a composite list of the features of what they term the 'improving school' a 'school that carry on to improve student learning consequences for all students over time.'Hallinger and Heck, School leadership strategies pay attention to the desired outcomes, but participation is always aided by other people, events, and administrative factors such as teacher commitment, instructional techniques, and school culture. This interpretation is accurate in the sense that leaders accomplish their goals mostly through and with the help of other people. Cooper et al. (2016, 87). Grissom and Loeb (2011, p. 1119) refer toin effect school leaders as leaders who bring about to combine and comprehend the instructional prerequisites of the school, have the capability to distributepossessions where they are needed, hire and be able to qualitative personnel and keep the school running. The starring role of the teacher leader – what it is and how it is demarcated – is varied, depending on the school perspective and the research. Yet, most scholars come to an agreement that teacher leadership take place within and outside classrooms to influence school-wide instructional practice. Robertson (2013) claims that it makes a substantialdissimilarity whether school leaders think that they are part of the change process or they think that the change process is about others. It's not simply about gaining more knowledge when it comes to leadership. It must also create opportunities for leaders to reveal more about a variety of different forms of knowledge. Metacognitive abilities can assist an individual leader in comprehending what new knowledge means for school leadership practise and for the development of the individual's uniqueness as a school leader. School leadership has been discussed in the literature in the context of various types of leadership. The types of leadership discussed extensively include instructional leadership, managerial leadership, transformational leadership, moral and authentic leadership, distributed leadership, teacher leadership, system leadership, and contingent leadership (Bush & Glover, 2014). Inclusive leadership demands different talents and abilities than a more directive and less invitational style of leadership. A crucial skill for leaders is to see leadership as a practise and to learn from day-to-day practise.Distributed leadership emphasises interdependence over reliance, and it involves the many ways in which different types of leaders share responsibilities. It promotes schools to be more open and collaborative, and it is the type of leadership that has been linked to better educational outcomes the most. Teachers' participation in collaboratively leading and influencing instructional and institutional development is the key to successful distributed leadership. It is obvious that people in formal leadership positions must continue to do specific responsibilities and activities, but teachers' participation in collaboratively leading and influencing instructional and institutional development is the key to successful leadership (Obadara, 2013).In order to effectively serve children, school leadership preparation must evolve with the times.The changing social, economic, and policy contexts in which schools operate further challenge educational leadership. Critical transformations in school demographics, hybrid school governance systems, accountability frameworks, and the professionalisation of teaching are all important factors shaping this environment.

Areas of Innovative Practices in School Administration

Leadership is now seen as a promise of better teaching quality, a critical component of school capacity expansion, and a significant contributor to creativity practise. Despite the fact that numerous leadership studies demonstrate the importance of leadership by demonstrating what leaders must do or how leadership practises should be provided in order for schools to succeed, less attention has been paid to how leadership is exercised and how it becomes consequential in social practises (Vennebo& Ottesen, 2012).

Planned Planning also known as group planning. It strives to obtain a consensus among "top people" in the school organization about the direction the school should run within a given period of time. The "top people" used here refers to the school administrator, and the heads of units or departments and some experienced teachers. During strategic or planned planning, the following things are done:

- Objectives are set for using unfilled resources.
- Policies are framed for attaining these objectives.
- Goings-on to be carried out are identified.
- The activities are systematized into groups.
- Teachers/non-teachers are as long as to perform these activities to accomplish the set objectives.
- Provision for appealing and permitting personnel to initiate work activities.

- Provision for inducements to raise your spirits for commitment to work, to the organization and high productivity.
- Provision for control measures and assessment of achievement of objectives.
- Provision for helpful actions in case of dearth in achieving the set objectives.

Innovation

A principal who fosters creativity in teachers and allows them to lead in their classrooms can instil innovation in a school's culture. The ability of the institution to innovate and progress is based on its creativity and learning capacities. It's been said that creativity is at the heart of leadership, but what does being imaginative as an instructional leader entail? Innovative leaders frequently exhibit emotional vitality and passion, have a social conscience, and the courage to think and act in unconventional ways. These characteristics show leadership potential, but only effective action can allow the leader to translate these characteristics into meaningful and purposeful achievements. This effective transformation is required for leadership; else, even the most skilled leaders will be rendered ineffective (Malik, 2014).

Good ideas can be generated by a large group of people. Followers should be motivated, reinforced, guided, and assisted by their leaders. It is the overview of new ideas, methods, strategies and procedures for doing things into the school for the purpose of improving the school's efficiency in both domains internal as well as external. Uchendu (2015) states innovation as a practice in which old or ineffective practices are being replaced by new programmes or practices.

The four types of innovation are:

- 1) **Service innovation:** It is the outline of new service which importantly powers and progresses the management practices in schools.
- 2) **Process innovation:** It is the putting into practice of a new or improved service delivery. This process in school proposed to lessen unit cost of service delivery and to develop or increase quality.
- 3) **Marketing innovation:** It involves the carrying out of a new marketing technique involving substantial changes in product design or product preferment or pricing.
- 4) **Organizational innovation:** This involves implementing a new organizational method in the school business management practices. This type of innovation is proposed to increase workforce contentment and good human productivity, assurance and participation among employees.

According to Baregheh et al. (2009: 1334), "Innovation is that the multi-stage process whereby organizations make over ideas into improved products, service or processes, so as to advance, contend and tell apart themselves successfully in their marketplace." in keeping with Isaksen & Akkermans (2011) provide the outline of innovation as "the planning, invention, development and/or implementation of latest or altered products, services, processes, systems, organizational structures, or business models for the aim of manufacturing new value for patrons and financial returns for the firm".

Due to expertise and innovation according to Wagner (2013), the secondary school leaders prerequisite the following 21st century skills: Emotional intelligence, Critical thinking and analytical skills, Creativity and innovation, Personal and communication skills, Technological skill, Organization skills, Personal management skills, Team work and collaboration, Partnership development, Community outreach, development and engagement, Ant-racism, equity and inclusiveness, Global awareness and understanding.

Lindgren and Abdullah (2013) have recommended a five-element innovation leadership model for a company to commendably implement innovation leadership. The elements to consider are: 1) The assignment of innovation leadership; 2) The field of innovation leadership, 3) The accomplishment criteria for the company's innovation leadership task; 4) The model of innovation leadership used in the company and 5) The process of innovation leadership.

The teachers must accept the principal's policies, rules, and regulations for administering the school. Teachers should be able to discuss any issues with the principal and make decisions. In the same way, the instructor should promote pupils' creativity and allow them to try new things. Teachers should be rewarded for their efforts with incentives, promotions, and recognition. The efforts of the kids should also be recognised. The educational policy and curriculum should be in line with the existing culture's values and customs. Teachers become loyal to an institute as their professional development progresses, and they work diligently. If it is a learning setting, the classroom culture might be diverse. Students' learning is aided by a variety of teaching methods. Engage the pupils in an exercise that requires them to solve an issue. Distributed leadership is the modern era's need; it empowers employees and allows them to realise their potential. Finding problems and working on them can be made easier using action research. Only an inventive plan can be adopted if all of these factors have been addressed. The continual evaluation of the innovation process is also required after deployment.

3. CONCLUSION

The present review paper aimed at contributing to the systematization and accumulation of research findings in the field of innovative practices and school leadership. A systematic method was employed to select and review research papers. The focus upon leadership has included different backgrounds and assumptions. Some have influenced the attitudes and behaviours of individuals, intrapersonal and interpersonal interaction for the purpose of achieving goals. Some is situation based, as they are totally dependent on situation like power and authority, interpersonal links, structure of

task assigned to group leader. Leadership plays a great role for enhancement of creativity, innovative projects for effectiveness of school leadership. Leadership behaviour can be well organised by practice and it makes a significant difference to the learning and achievements of students. Innovative practices and strategies in school leadership have influence on the effectiveness of leaders with reference to their potential of leading and it is associated with certain goals. Through innovative leadership practices, one can solve problems related to future, get benefited and will lead to change. The autonomy and value-added methods make similar attempts to improve the responsibilities of school leaders. Regardless, these change agents are frequently faced with a power struggle: whether to lead alone or with others. Due to the enigma of leadership, school leaders must be able to find a balance between competing responsibilities and ideals. As part of their leadership responsibilities, school administrators must understand and commit to curricular, instructional, and organisational strategies that enable all children to achieve academic success. It is just as important for school administrators to have the determination and courage to put their knowledge into practise as it is to know what to do. It's possible that educational systems will remain cumbersome and coordinated.

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